

NOVEL CYCLIC OLEFIN COPOLYMER/EPOXY BLEND FOR THERMAL MENDING OF EPOXY IN CARBON FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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Introduction

- Composite materials have **some serious drawbacks** :
 - Low interlaminar fracture toughness.
 - Low impact resistance due to the low ductility and strength of the thermoset polymer matrix.
- **Matrix and delamination cracking** could occur from edge stresses, environmental degradation or aging.
- In general, delaminations, microcracks and cracks **are hard to be detected at an early stage**, and could cause unexpected catastrophic failure.

- **Self-healing materials**
- built-in ability to **automatically repair damage** present in their structures, with or without any external intervention.

Introduction

Thermoplastic-thermosetting blend

Miscible blends

Polybisphenol-A-co-epichlorohydrin (Hayes et. al)

Miscible blends having thermoplastic phase dissolved in the thermosetting matrix.

Immiscible blends either a thermoset phase embedded in a thermoplastic matrix (PIPS) or particulate thermoplastic phase embedded in a thermoset matrix.

PIPS: Polymerization-induced phase separation

Immiscible blends

Polycaprolactone (PCL)
(Karger et al.)

Poly (ether sulfone) (Kim et al.)

Polyetherimide (Wang et al.)

Poly (methyl methacrylate)
(Cabanelas et al.)

The use of semi-crystalline polymer to create blends, hence the necessity to melt the polymer.

Thermoplastic-thermosetting blend

Particle-dispersed blend

Polyethylene-co-methacrylic acid
(EMAA) (Muere et al.)

85% recovery (critical stress intensity)

Linear thermoplastic polycaprolactone diol (Li et al.)

61% after 5 healing cycles

Copolyester (Nji et al.)

75% recovery

Previously used polymers to create particle dispersed blends, limited recovery in the matrix.

Objective

- **Addition of COC (amorphous thermoplastic)** as a healing agent in epoxy.
- **Preparation of epoxy/COC blends** at different wt.% concentrations (10, 20, 30, 40%).
- Evaluation of the **effect of the COC addition** on the **thermo-mechanical properties** of the resulting blends.
- Evaluation of the **self-healing properties** of the prepared matrix.
- Wet lay-up method for **CF reinforced composite fabrication**.
- Evaluation of the **self-healing properties** of the prepared composite using above prepared blends.

Similar properties of COC
as epoxy

Properties	Epoxy	COC
Solid phase	Amorphous	Amorphous
Glass transition temperature (T_g) ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	84	80
Tensile modulus (MPa)	3100	2250
Tensile strength (MPa)	56	45
Strain at break (tensile) (%)	7	5

Materials and methods – Epoxy/COC blends

Polymer

Epoxy bicomponent system provided by Elantas Srl (Collecchio, Italy)

Elan-tech® EC157 (Base)
Elan-tech® W342 (Hardner)

100:30 (mass ratio)

Curing cycle: 24 h at RT + 15 h at 60°C.

Healing agent

Cyclo olefin copolymer (COC 8007) provided by TOPAS, grounded and sieved to less than 300 μm.

- **Preparation of EP/COC blends**
- COC granules were directly introduced into liquid nitrogen and cryogenically grinded, until 300 μm particles were achieved.
- Mixing EP base with COC powder (speed = 3000 rpm, $T = 50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $t = 1\text{ h}$)
- After degassing, the hardener was added base/hardener ratio of 100:30.
- The mixtures were poured into different silicon moulds
- Curing cycle: 24 h at $23\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ + 15 h at $60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

Materials	Resin (%)	Hardener (%)	COC microparticles (%)
EP	76.9	23.1	-----
EP/COC-10%	69.2	20.8	10
EP/COC-20%	61.5	18.5	20
EP/COC-30%	53.8	16.2	30
EP/COC-40%	46.0	14.0	40

Thermal treatment of the samples – Epoxy/COC blends

- After the curing process, EP/COC samples were divided in two groups.
- Untreated samples (**u-samples**)
- Thermally treated samples at 190°C for 1 h in the furnace (**t-samples**)
- **Separate the effect** of the thermal treatment to that produced by the healing.

→ untreated samples (u)

→ thermally treated samples (t)

- A change in color due to the oxydation of the epoxy resin was observed.
- The transparency was compromised due to the increased concentration of COC.

Healing evaluation – Epoxy/COC blends

- Fracture behavior under three point bending and Charpy impact conditions
- Three point bending tests on notched specimens
- Key fracture parameters on SENB specimens were evaluated (K_{IC} and G_{IC})

Healing process

$T = 190\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$
 $t = 1\text{ h}$
 $P = 15\text{ MPa}$

Apparent healing efficiency (η)

$$\eta = \frac{K_{IC, \text{healed samples}}}{K_{IC, u - \text{virgin samples}}}$$

Real healing efficiency (η')

$$\eta' = \frac{K_{IC, \text{healed samples}}}{K_{IC, t - \text{virgin samples}}}$$

Separate the effect of the **thermal treatment** to that produced by the **healing**

Materials and methods – Epoxy/COC/CF composite

Matrix

Epoxy bicomponent system provided by Elantas Srl (Collecchio, Italy)

Elan-tech® EC157 (Base)

Elan-tech® W342 (Hardner)

100:30 (mass ratio)

Curing cycle: 24 h at RT + 15 h at 60°C.

Healing agent

Cyclo olefin copolymer (COC 8007) provided by TOPAS, grounded and sieved to less than 300 μm.

Reinforcement

Carbon fibers (GV-201 TFX by G. Angeloni Srl) nominal areal weight of 218 g/m².

	Warp	Weft
Fiber description	HS Carbon Fiber HTS 40 F13 - 12K	Thermoplastic Coated Glass Yarn, Glass Yarn - 1100dtex
Weight distribution	92%	8%

Composite fabrication - Epoxy/COC/CF composite

- Mechanical mixing of COC powder in epoxy resin (10, 20 and 30 wt. % in epoxy matrix) for 1 h at 50°C.
- Nominal fiber weight fraction of 50% using relative amounts of each components.
- Wet lay-up method, consolidated by vacuum bagging process swiftly followed by compression (0.8 MPa) under hot-press.
- Curing performed under compression with a curing cycle of 24h at RT + 15h at 60°C.
- Nomenclature of samples as:

Composite	COC wt%
EP/CF	0%
EP10COC/CF	10%
EP20COC/CF	20%
EP30COC/CF	30%

- Fracture toughness of composites evaluated in opening mode using ASTM D5528-01 of double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens.
- Instron® 5969 using 50kN load cell.
- Crosshead speed of 2.5mm/min.
- Crack advancement monitored using a webcam.
- 14 laminate composites prepared having thickness varying between 2.8 to 4.8mm.
- Precrack by insertion of PET foil of 26 µm.
- G_I calculated according to modified beam theory (MBT):

$$G_I = \frac{3P\delta}{2ba}$$

where

P = load

δ = extension

b = width

a = delamination length

- Fractured specimen repaired at 190°C for 1 h under a compression of 0.5 MPa.
- Lab-prepared screw device used to close the crack using a torque screwdriver.

- The repair efficiency (η) was determined as a ratio of interlaminar fracture toughness of repaired specimen to the interlaminar fracture toughness of virgin specimen :

$$\eta = \frac{G_{IR}}{G_{IV}}$$

Results and discussion – Epoxy/COC blends

- Viscosity analysis
- Optical microscopy
- Tensile testing
- Mode I fracture toughness test
 - a) Testing and healing
 - b) Evaluation of healing efficiency

Brookfield viscosimeter (RVT) , spindle No. 21 (SC4-21/13R)

8 ml of uncured resin

- The viscosity of uncured EP resin progressively increases with the COC amount.
- The workability of the resins is more difficult at elevated COC concentrations.

- LEICA Axiophot Optical Microscope (samples polished by abrasive SiC paper)

(u)

(t)

- Homogeneous dispersion of COC domains within the resin
- The dimensions of COC domains does not depend by COC amount
- A slight reduction in size of COC particles is observed after thermal treatment

Tensile testing - Epoxy /COC blends

- **Decrease of the tensile properties with the COC amount.**
- **Negative deviation with respect to the rule of mixture.**
- Tensile properties **were significantly enhanced after thermal treatment** (further crosslinking of the resin).

Quasi-static conditions

Three point bending tests on notched specimens ($v = 10 \text{ mm/min}$, ASTM D-5045)

Impact conditions

Charpy impact tests on notched specimens ($v = 1 \text{ m/s}$, ISO 179-2)

Evaluation of the maximum load (P_{max})

Quasi-static conditions

Impact conditions

- **Progressive increase in P_{max} as a function of the COC content**, both under quasi-static and impact conditions, was observed for virgin, treated and healed samples.
- **Thermal treatment determines a slight increase of the P_{max} values**, both under quasi-static and impact conditions.
- **At elevated COC concentrations, P_{max} of healed samples is very near to that of virgin samples (very good healing efficiency).**

Evaluation of the critical stress intensity factor (K_{IC})

- K_{IC} of t-virgin samples is slightly higher than that of u-virgin samples, both under quasi-static and impact conditions.
- K_{IC} of healed samples increases with the COC amount, both under quasi-static and impact conditions (toughening effect of COC).
- At elevated COC concentrations, K_{IC} of healed samples is very near to that of virgin samples (very good healing efficiency).

Quasi-static conditions

Samples	Healing efficiency [%]	
	η	η'
EP	26.2±10.3	22.8±9.2
EP/CO-10%	56.9±6.1	52.9±5.6
EP/COC-20%	72.3±13.7	66.4±7.6
EP/COC-30%	87.3±9.2	79.8±7.2
EP/COC-40%	118.6±17.6	88.7±10.5

Impact conditions

Samples	Healing efficiency [%]	
	η	η'
EP	---	---
EP/COC-10%	51.2±3.6	45.5±3.3
EP/COC-20%	89.2±10.7	82.7±6.9
EP/COC-30%	95.0±5.3	92.5±14.1
EP/COC-40%	102.7±16.5	97.4±9.5

- Increase of η (healing + thermal treatment) and η' (only healing) with the COC concentration, both under quasi-static and impact conditions.
- The real healing efficiency (η') of the EP/COC-40% sample is very close to 100%, both under quasi-static and impact conditions.
- The effect of the thermal treatment of the samples, determined as the difference between η and η' , is not so pronounced.

Possible use of COC as an effective healing agent for epoxy matrices.

Results and discussion – Epoxy/COC/CF composite

- Morphological analysis
- Thermogravimetric analysis
- Mechanical properties
 - Short beam shear (SBS) test
 - Flexural test
- Mode I fracture toughness test
 - a) Testing and healing
 - b) Evaluation of healing efficiency

Morphological analysis - Epoxy/COC/CF composite

Longitudinal view

Cross-sectional view

EP/CF

EP10COC/CF

EP20COC/CF

EP30COC/CF

- Distribution of COC particles between the laminates hence **creating disruption of the fiber orientation.**
- Irregular shaped particles of COC due to its **amorphous structure.**
- **Presence of voids** in the laminates due to increased COC content.

Thermogravimetric analysis - Epoxy/COC/CF composite

Mettler TG50 thermobalance, 35-700°C @ 10°C/min,
Nitrogen flux = 100ml/ml

- Composite specimens (~40mg) having 16 CF laminates.
- Void content in composites calculated by archimedes method.
- Density of carbon fiber determined by Helium pycnometer (MicromeriticsVR Accupyc 1330 helium pycnometer).

Weight percentages

	%CF	%EP	%COC
EP/CF	72.8	27.3	0
EP10COC/CF	66.8	25.2	8.0
EP20COC/CF	60.6	22.4	17.0
EP30COC/CF	50.4	25.7	23.9

Volumetric percentages

	%CF	%Matrix	%Voids
EP/CF	63.2	31.7	5.1
EP10COC/CF	55.7	34.1	10.2
EP20COC/CF	48.4	39.3	12.2
EP30COC/CF	38.1	52.9	9.0

- **More matrix content** due to more increased COC content, hence **lowered CF content** in COC based composites.
- **Increased void content** due to high viscosity of the blend.

Short beam shear (SBS) test - Epoxy/COC/CF composite

- Instron® 5969 using 50kN load cell.
- Determination of interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) according to ASTM D2344 – 16.
- Composite specimens having 16 CF laminates.

- **Thickness increased** from 3 to 5 mm with increased COC content.
- **Lowering of ILSS** being contributed by the lowering of CF content.

Flexural properties - Epoxy/COC/CF composite

- Instron® 5969 using 50kN load cell.
- Tested according to ASTM D790-15.
- Composite with 4 CF laminates.
- Modulus determined at 60:1 span-thickness ratio while strength determined at 40:1 ratio.

• **Thickness variation:** 1 to 1.4mm

• Lowered CF content, **Lowered flexural properties.**

Healing evaluation - Epoxy/COC/CF composite

- Fractured specimen **repaired at 190°C for 1 h** under a compression of 0.5 MPa.
- **Lab-prepared screw device** used to close the crack using a torque screwdriver.

- Thin EP/CF composite showed **less rigidity** due to thin nature of the composite
- COC content $\geq 20\%$ **offered even more toughness** after healing compared to virgin specimen.
- **Possible contributing factors** include:
 - Better fracture toughness of COC compared to epoxy.
 - Improved cross-linking of epoxy.
 - Improved adhesion between the epoxy and COC particles.

Healing evaluation - Epoxy/COC/CF composite

- Average G_I of either virgin or repaired calculated by fitting the curve according to the **asymptotic model** according to the formula $y = a - bc^x$

- The repair efficiency (η) was determined as a **ratio of interlaminar fracture toughness of repaired specimen to the interlaminar fracture toughness of virgin specimen** :

$$\eta = \frac{G_{IR}}{G_{IV}}$$

Fractured specimen morphology - Healing evaluation - Epoxy/COC/CF composite

Virgin

Healed

EP/CF

EP10COC/CF

EP20COC/CF

EP30COC/CF

Random distribution of COC particles between fibers and the matrix.
Variation of relative COC content in the laminates.

2nd healing efficiency - Healing evaluation - Epoxy/COC/CF composite

1 st repair	
Healing efficiency (%)	
EP/CF	8.3
EP10COC/CF	58.9
EP20COC/CF	222.5
EP30COC/CF	269.6
2 nd repair	
Healing efficiency (%)	
EP20COC/CF	116.1
EP30COC/CF	117.2

EP20COC/CF

EP30COC/CF

- **Only EP20COC/CF and EP30COC/CF** healed specimens fractured and healed again with the same conditions
- Previously healed specimens showed **lowered second healing efficiency**.
- Lowered second healing efficiency could be attributed to the **second thermal treatment**.

Epoxy/COC
blend

Epoxy/COC
/CF
composite

- **For the first time**, the self-healing properties of EP/COC blends were investigated.
- The introduction of COC **progressively increased the K_{Ic} of the samples**, both under quasi-static and impact conditions, and thermal treatment contributed to the increase the K_{Ic} .
- **Increase of the healing efficiency** with the COC concentration, both under quasi-static and impact conditions. The real healing efficiency of the EP/COC-40% sample is very close to 100%.
- The ILSS and flexural properties **decreased with increased amount of COC** due to the lowered CF content in the composite.
- **Determination of healing efficiencies** in terms of toughness was evaluated using Mode I fracture toughness test on DCB specimens.
- Dispersed COC particles in the composite assisted in the recovery of fracture toughness of the composites on multiple healing events where the **first healing efficiency surpassing 200%** in case of 20% and 30% of COC content in EP/CF composites.

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